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доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Бухарского государственного медицинского
института. (Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

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Ташкентской медицинской академии.
(Узбекистан).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

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Chief Editor:

Khodjueva Dilbar Tadjiyevna

Doctor of medical Sciences, Professor,
Bukhara state medical Institute. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5883-9533

Deputy editor-in-chief:

Khaydarova Dildora Kadirovna

Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor of the Tashkent
Medical Academy. (Uzbekistan).
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4980-6158

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Kamalova Malika Ilkhomovna
Rakhmonova Mohigul Shodikulovna
Samarkand State Medical University

EXAM STRESS OF STUDENTS AND METHODS OF ITS OVERCOMING

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ANNOTATION

The article deals with the main factors of students' stress, the dynamics of its course. The results of students' examination of exam stress; practical methods of correction used by students to relieve mental tension are presented.

Keywords: exam stress, stress factors, students

Камалова Малика Илхомовна
Рахмонова Мохигул Шодикуловна
Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

ЭКЗАМЕНАЦИОННЫЙ СТРЕСС СТУДЕНТОВ И МЕТОДЫ ЕГО ПЕРЕОДОЛЕНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются основные факторы стресса студентов, динамика его протекания. Представлены результаты обследования студентов по изучению экзаменационного стресса; практические методы коррекции, которыми пользуются студенты для снятия психической напряженности.

Ключевые слова: экзаменационный стресс, факторы стресса, студенты

Kamalova Malika Ilkhomovna
Rahmonova Mohigul Shodikulovna
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

TALABALARNING IMTIHON STRESSI VA UNI YENGISH USULLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada talabalarning asosiy stress omillari va uning rivojlanish dinamikasi muhokama qilingan. Imtihon stressini o'rganish bo'yicha talabalar so'rovi natijalari taqdim etilgan; aqliy zo'riqishni yengillashirish uchun talabalar orqali foydalanadigan amaliy tuzatish usullari qo'llanilagan.

Kalit so'zlar: imtihon stressi, stress omillari, talabalar

Introduction. Exam stress occupies one of the first places among the reasons causing mental stress in higher education students. Very often the exam becomes a psychotraumatic factor that has a negative impact on the nervous, cardiovascular and immune systems of students [7].

Exam stress, especially in combination with caffeine consumption, can lead to a persistent increase in blood pressure in students, and pronounced disorders of autonomic regulation of the cardiovascular system are registered [2].

The unfavourable factors of preparation for exams include: intensive mental activity; increased static load; extreme restriction of motor activity; sleep disorders; emotional stress associated with the upcoming exams, etc. All these factors lead to overstrain.

All this leads to overstrain of the autonomic nervous system, which regulates the normal vital activity of the human body. During the exam the heart rate increases significantly, blood pressure, muscle and psycho-emotional tension level increases. After passing the exam, physiological parameters do not immediately return to normal, it takes several days for these parameters to return to their initial values.

Consequently, exam stress is a serious threat to the health of students, covering hundreds of thousands of students nationwide [6].

At the same time, scientists note that exam stress is not always harmful ('distress') [5]. In certain situations, psychological stress can have a stimulating value, helping the student to mobilise all his knowledge and personal reserves to pass the exam. In this case, it is necessary to optimise (correct) the level of exam stress in over-anxious students with excessively labile psyche and, possibly, slightly increase it in inert, low-motivated students of higher education.

Purpose of the research: to study the students' exam stress and its dynamics we have developed a special experiment consisting of three stages.

Materials and methods of research: At the first stage of the experiment with the help of the developed form 'Questionnaire for studying the examination stress of students and the dynamics of its course' the 1st year students in the number of 41 people (32 girls, 9 boys) were examined.

At the second stage, with the help of psychological tests that contribute to the measurement of students' tension and personality traits, the measurement of these indicators in normal conditions of activity was

carried out. In order to measure the dynamics of students' mental tension, this tension was measured before the beginning, five minutes after the start of the simulated exam, fifteen minutes later and after the performance of a difficult task. On the obtained data base of psychological techniques, a correlation analysis was carried out in order to identify correlations of students' personality traits with indicators of stress level.

At the third stage, the final stage, practical methods of stress correction were developed, with which the students were familiarised.

According to the first question of the questionnaire, contributing to the identification of students' knowledge about emotional states, to the question "How do you understand the concept of "mental tension" the examinees answered as follows: tense uncomfortable state of the organism, nervousness, dissatisfaction - 38 people (92.8%); fatigue - 2 people (4.8%); low sociability - 1 person (2.4%).

To the second question of the questionnaire "How do you understand the concept of "Stress", the surveyed indicated that it is: the highest point of emotional tension - 21 people (51.2%); depressed state of mind, no way out - 14 people (34.1%); mental and physical disorder - 5 people (12.2%); time deficit - 1 person (2.4%).

Students feel mental tension in their organism as follows: it is impossible to work in full force, discomfort - 20 people (48.8%); inability to think about other tasks - 11 people (26.8%); headache - 8 people (19.5%); stiffness of movements, abdominal pain and palpitations - 6 people (14.6%); appetite changes (increases or worsens, hand tremors, irritability - 4 people (9.8%); sleep disturbance - 3 people (7.3%). (14,6 %); appetite changes (increases or worsens), hands

tremor, irritability appears - 4 people (9,8 %); sleep is disturbed - 3 people (7,3 %); breathing changes, internal shivering, chills - 2 people (4,9 %); thirst appears - 1 person (2,4 %). One student does not feel mental tension, which makes 2.4 %.

On the questionnaire "How do you behave in the state of stress" the students' opinions were divided as follows: they make a plan of action to overcome it - 19 people (46,3 %); think over the situation - 17 people (41,5 %); talk about the difficult situation with friends and relatives - 13 people (31,7 %); panic - 1 person (2,4 %); go for sports - 1 person (2,4 %).

The plannedness of students' preparation for classes was determined by the questionnaire with the question: "Do you regularly prepare for classes during the academic year?"

The 4th year students answered to this question that they prepare regularly for a seminar or practice - 24 (58,5 %); preparation depends on the teacher's requirements - 14 (34,2 %); they prepare irregularly - 5 (12,2 %); two students prepare every day for classes and two students do not prepare for them at all - 4,9 %.

Students begin to feel the approach of the examination session during the credit week - 18 students (43.9%), about a month in advance - 9 students (21.9%), when preparing for the first examination - 6 students (14.6%), always thinking about it - 2 students (4.9%).

The structure of students' preparation for exams was determined by the proposed statements, which they evaluated on a 10-point scale, the average ratings of which, their rank and these statements are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Average assessments of exam preparation activities of the group of examinees

№	Sayings	Average score
1	Preparing on my own	9,8
2	Going to counselling	4,9
3	Working on the Internet	4,0
4	Making phone calls	3,9
5	Preparing with a friend	2,8
6	Go to libraries	2,6
7	Make time for yourself	1.2

It follows from the analysis of Table 1 that students rank the factor 'independent preparation' first, the factor 'counselling' second, the factor 'Internet' third, and the factor 'calling a friend' fourth. Such actions of students to obtain knowledge as 'preparing with someone', 'library', 'paid services' rank from 5th to 7th, defining them as ineffective actions.

In order to reveal the dynamics of stress reactions, the examinees were asked to evaluate their mental tension on the day of the exam. Analysing it is possible to say that the average estimation of mental tension when students leave home is 5.5 points on a 10-point scale, reaching the maximum - 7.1 points before the door of the classroom, and when the exam ticket is taken - 6.9 points. If students know the answers to the questions of the ticket, the average tension of students immediately decreases from 6.9 points to the value of 3.5, if the knowledge for the answer. In addition, during the answer to the teacher on the questions of the exam ticket students feel mobilising mental tension (4.4 points), contributing to the concentration of attention and physical strength to successfully pass the intellectual test.

Results of the study After successfully passing the exam and leaving the classroom students feel a slight mental tension of two points, but by the evening this tension decreases to one point.

From the analysis of students' answers to the questionnaire, which was used to determine students' actions to correct their emotional states, it follows that students correct (reduce) their mental tension before exams, during exams, and after them in various ways known to them.

Before the exams, students make themselves believe that everything will be fine, try to repeat more - 22 people (53 %); take sedatives; try to eat well - 2 people (4.9 %); listen to music; take breaks in preparation;

no other methods help - 1 person (2.4 %). Only three people remain absolutely calm, which is 7.3% of the whole group of examinees.

During exams students in order to reduce their stress 'try to look good, be confident, concentrate, maintain even and deep breathing' - 19 people (46.3%); 'just prepare' - 4 people (9.8%); 'look out of the window' - 3 people (7.3%); drink water - 1 person (2.4%). As only one person indicated in the questionnaire, he does not feel stress at all, which is 2.4 % of the whole group of surveyed students.

After passing exams, students in order to relieve residual stress phenomena identified that they 'communicate with friends, go out, joke' - 24 people (58.5%); 'need rest, sleep' - 6 people (17.1%); 'tension passes by itself' - 5 people (14.6%); 'listen to music' - 3 (7.3%); 'use valerian' - 2 (4.7%); 'go to the bath' - 1 person (2.4%). One student, as he indicated in the questionnaire, has no mental tension after the exam (2.4 %). We have given only the indicators of four people from the group of thirty-seven examinees.

Table 3 shows that the examinees labelled with numbers 1 and 2 had a decrease in situational anxiety by (-14) and (-12) points respectively five minutes after the beginning of the difficult task. Other students of the group labelled with numbers 36 and 37, on the contrary, situational anxiety increased by (15) and (20) points respectively.

From the analysis of the obtained statistical correlations of factors M 'dreaminess - practicality' and <34 'tension - relaxation' with changes in situational anxiety 'delta' it follows that the corresponding correlation coefficients are positive and equal to $\hat{r} = 0.27$ and $\hat{r} = 0.21$.

Such a positive statistical correlation $\hat{r} = 0.27$ contributes to the assumption that individuals with high scores on the factor 'M', defined as 'having a rich imagination, immersed in themselves, absorbed in their ideas and fantasies' under the influence of a tense situation are more

susceptible to stress than students with low scores on this factor, 'characterised by maturity, poise, sanity' [4].

The correlation coefficient $r = 0.21$ between factor <34 and 'delta' contributes to the determination that students with high scores on factor <34, defined as 'being in a state of excitement, tension, having difficulty calming down, feeling defeated', are also more susceptible to stress than students with low scores on this factor, defined as 'relaxed, imperturbable, calm about failures and fortunes' [5]. The RA factor (performing arithmetic counting tasks) also has a positive correlation coefficient with the indicators of situational anxiety change 'delta'. The revealed statistical correlation contributes to the assumption that students who carry out great thinking activity, who perform well on tasks with large numbers, who have high mathematical intelligence, are more susceptible to stress loads than their peers who have more modest mathematical abilities.

For students who have high scores on factors G (responsibility, commitment) and MD (desire to look in a favourable light), the peculiarity is a decrease in the effect of a stressful situation on their mental tension, as their correlation coefficients with the dynamics of stress increase 'delta' are negative.

From the analysis of statistical correlations of 24 personality indicators of students with their changes of situational anxiety under the action of performance of difficult academic tasks only 4 personality factors have coefficients of

correlation coefficients in the range ($0.2 = R < 0.3$), contributing to the determination of a weak statistical relationship between students' personality traits and their regulation of their emotional states.

Consequently, the research conducted with the help of psychological tests did not reveal large correlations between students' personality characteristics and their ability to optimise the stress load arising during exams.

This result can be explained, for example, by the fact that each student reacts differently to the examination ticket taken for the answer, for an unprepared student it will be a stressor and may cause discomfort, heart palpitations, chills, feeling of thirst, etc., while a student who knows the study material may not notice this stressor [6]. Exam stress is an inseparable part of a student's social adaptation during education. As a result of the conducted research, it can be concluded that there are characteristics of student's personality that determine their successful adaptation to the most diverse conditions. These characteristics are formed in the process of their whole life: neuropsychic stability, self-esteem of personality, feeling of their importance for others, level of conflict, experience of communication, moral and ethical orientation, orientation to the requirements of the immediate environment, etc.

Thus, the leading way to optimise excessive emotional tension is the harmonious development of a person's personality, the formation of an independent outlook, professionalism of activity.

Practical methods of correction are based on the following provisions: adaptation takes place at all levels of human organisation, including the mental sphere; mental adaptation is a central link in the general adaptation of a person, since it is the nature of mental regulation that determines the nature of adaptation as a whole [6].

Very often unfavourable consequences arise in students not because of the cases themselves, but because of the reaction to them.

The main ways to get out of a tense situation are:

- changing or eliminating the problem; reducing the impact of the problem by shifting the point of view to another object, more pleasant; alleviating the impact of stress through practical methods of correction; choosing the right moment to make a decision or realise one's plan; weakening motivation; correctly assessing the event in progress;

preparing pre-prepared strategies of retreat; pointlessness of fighting with an already fait accompli.

It has been established by human practice that the ability to relax contributes significantly to the reduction of psycho-emotional tension and emotional instability. The ability to relax, subjectively and psychologically influence muscle tone is the most important condition for the removal of excitement caused by anxiety [3].

Relaxation methods are: neuromuscular relaxation, arbitrary regulation of breathing, biofeedback, meditation, autogenic training.

Behavioural methods of correction of a stressful state of personality are used to form a new stereotype of behaviour, which was not previously present in human activity. Physical stress is regulated by us, so it is necessary, as I.P. Pavlov taught, to 'drive passion into the muscles'. Methods of relaxation and breathing are expedient to apply when it is necessary to quickly bring oneself to a calm state.

Behavioural methods of correction of the stress state of a person contribute to the formation of new social skills, mastery of psychological techniques of self-regulation, overcoming bad habits, stress relief, getting rid of emotional traumas, etc. A special place in the correction of mental tension is played by a person's smile. Kept on the face, it improves mood. Smile helps to increase the amount of arterial blood flowing through the brain, i.e. supplying the brain with oxygen. Laughter can also serve as a means of releasing emotional tension. The general effect of moderate laughter is that the brain is more intensively released from metabolic products, and therefore there is a feeling of a rested person. Also one of the important ways to relieve psychological tension is considered to be a sense of humour. The essence of the sense of humour is not to see the comic where it is, but to perceive as comic serious, exciting situations. Laughter is good at reducing the effects of psychological tension. After laughter, a person's muscles are less tense, heartbeat normalises. A kind of relaxation takes place [6].

Autogenic training methods have been developed to normalise the activity of the cardiovascular system, respiration, internal organs, in case of diseases: prevention of myocardial infarction, after a heart attack, fatigue, stabilisation of blood pressure, kidney recovery, in case of migraine, for immunity to colds [1].

An effective method to relieve stress is the method of arbitrary regulation of breathing, through which a person consciously controls the number of breathing movements. Also, to reduce their mental tension, a student can create an illusory world where there is no sense of anxiety, engage in art, listen to calm music, go for a massage, go to a bath, exercise.

Conclusions: Thus, in preparation for examinations, the student should improve nutrition, contributing to the restoration of vitamin deficiency, and in the case of a strong impact on the emotional state of the learner of the upcoming examinations, he should consult a doctor, to carry out the reception of pharmacological means according to his prescription.

The effectiveness of the methods of correction on the student's emotional state can be determined through self-observation, which allows the student to record important mental signs of stress. This method proceeds from the fact that the personality should independently strive for a goal and influence its behaviour. Self-regulation of behaviour is carried out through processes that are enacted and maintained by the individual, i.e. cognitive modes of behaviour such as planning, thinking, etc.

Prediction of student's stress reactions to the examination procedure is impossible without detailed elaboration of both physiological and psychological components of examination stress with obligatory consideration of individual personal characteristics.

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Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

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